

Effect of Time on the Mechanical Behavior of Laminated Composites

S. Amijima¹⁾, T. Adachi²⁾

1) Department of Mechanical Engineering, Doshisha University, Imadegawa, Karasuma, Kamigyō-ku, Kyoto 602, Japan

2) Synthetic Resin Technical Laboratory, Dainippon Ink & Chemicals Inc., 3-1 Takasago, Takaishi-shi, Osaka 592, Japan

ABSTRACT

A predicting method to determine the time response of a unidirectional and cross plied polyester/glass composites is described. The short-term (20 minutes duration) creep test results of strip tension specimens with the load at various angles to the fiber direction are reported and compared to the analytical results. It is shown that the materials are elastic at all stress levels when the fibers are in the load direction. On the other hand, when the load is transverse to the fibers the viscoelastic response shows to vary from small amounts at low stress level to large amounts at high stress level even in a room temperature. For other fiber angles, the response is similar to the latter. And also the numerically predicted results are compared with experimental results. As the results, only two material informations are needed to predict the viscoelastic response of the composites. One is the viscoelastic response of the matrix resin and the other is the material constants of the matrix and reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are finding increasing use in the aerospace and automotive industries. These materials may exhibit time dependent mechanical behavior, depending upon the state of load, temperature, and relative humidity (1). Thus, it is necessary to measure the time dependent effects when the composites are to be used for structural applications. Plastics as a matrix are generally exhibit a large amount of creep comparing to glass fibers or carbon fibers as a reinforcement. Accordingly, a composite which is composed of a matrix resin and mineral fibers may possess an appreciable amount of time dependent characteristics. Viscoelastic flow in the matrix and internal flaw formation and growth are normally the main sources of the creep (2). Large stress concentrations exist in the matrix resin around the relatively hard and rigid fibers, and as a consequence, matrix cracks and fiber/matrix separation can occur at relatively low applied load. Significant viscoelastic flow, as well, often occurs in the matrix resin. This creep can be remarkably accelerated in the environment of high temperature and high relative humidity. However, polyester resin as a matrix, such as studied in this paper, has large amount of creep even in a room temperature.

The well developed linear viscoelastic theory can be applied to the characterization of polymeric materials only when the stress are sufficiently low.

This linear region is normally small comparing to the yielding or rupture of polymers (3, 4). However, a considerable amount of non linearity has been observed in a high stress level.

Our objective of this investigation is to predict and measure the viscoelastic response of the unidirectional laminate which is composed of a polyester resin and glass fibers. Further, another objective is to express the viscoelastic response of a off-axis unidirectional and cross plied laminates using viscoelastic response of the constituent laminae. To express the viscoelastic behavior of this material, the following assumptions are adopted. One is a viscoelasticity of a composite to be governed only by that of a matrix resin. The other assumption is that the Laminate Plate Theory (5) is realized even during creep stressed conditions.

NONLINEAR CONSTITUTIVE EQUATION

The general linear viscoelastic constitutive theory is well known Boltzmann's superposition integral:

$$e(t) = \int_0^t S_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\sigma(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau$$

$$= S_{ij}(0)\sigma(0) + \int_0^t \frac{dS_{ij}(t-\tau)}{d\tau} \sigma(\tau) d\tau \quad (1)$$

where $e, \sigma, t(\tau)$, and S_{ij} are the strain, stress, time, and linear viscoelastic creep compliance, respectively. And a general nonlinear constitutive theory for a uniaxial load from thermodynamic principles was developed by Lou and Schapery (1) as follows:

$$e(t) = g_0 S_{ij}(0)\sigma + g_1 g_2 \Delta S_{ij} \left(\frac{t}{a_\sigma} \right) \sigma \quad (2)$$

where g_0, g_1, g_2 , and a_σ are the stress-dependent nonlinear viscoelastic material properties and they are functions of stress. The creep strain of many metals and plastics obeys a power law in time. If the power law is assumed for a matrix resin, the transient component of the linear viscoelastic creep compliance is :

$$\Delta S_{ij} = C\psi^n \quad (3)$$

here, ψ is the stress reduced time. C and n are the independents of the stress level and time. Equations (2) and (3) yield the following formula:

$$e(t) = g_0 S_{ij}(0)\sigma + g_1 g_2 C \left(\frac{t}{a_\sigma} \right)^n \sigma \quad (4)$$

However it is too difficult to determine the material properties, g_1, g_2, C , and a_σ individually from a experiment. Therefore, new material property, K was incorporated as follows:

$$K = \frac{g_1 g_2 C \sigma}{a_\sigma^n} \quad (5)$$

The strain e can be expressed by using initial strain, e_0 and new property, K as shown in Figure 1.

$$e(t) = e_0 + Kt^n \quad (6)$$

From Equations (4) and (5), a nonlinear viscoelastic creep compliance, S_{ij}^{NL} is given by

$$S_{ij}^{NL}(t) = \frac{e(t)}{\sigma} = g_0 S_{ij}(0) + \frac{Kt^n}{\sigma} \quad (7)$$

and

$$S_{ij}^{NL}(t) = \frac{e_0 + Kt^n}{\sigma} \quad (8)$$

The material property, K and exponent of power law, n can be found together with a short term creep data and Equation (6).

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Materials

The materials used are summarized in Table 1. Three assortments of a resin and reinforcement are prepared for the specimen. Type A specimen is a polyester resin without a reinforcement. This specimen is used to estimate the creep characteristic of the matrix. Type B specimen is a unidirectional laminate and type C is a cross plied laminate in a right angle. These laminates are fabricated by a hand-lay-up method and regulated the same glass fiber content, $V_f=34\%$ by volume and the polyester are casted. Specimens are cut to the shape in Figure 2 from the fabricated panels. The stacking order of the specimen is detailed in Table 2. The tensile creep specimens are instrumented with two-element rectangular strain gages rosettes in order to record the strains of load and perpendicular to the load directions. Two rosettes are bonded to each specimen, one on each side, and the gage outputs are averaged to eliminate any out-of-plane bending.

Mechanical Conditioning

All the specimens are mechanically conditioned before tests in order to the same strain output under the same load for every creep test thereafter. The conditioning is achieved after ten cycles of one hour loading and one day recovery. It was shown by Desal and McGarry (6) that in the epoxy matrix of glass fiber composites tiny cracks occur during the first loading, even under sufficient low stress level comparing to the rupture stress.

Creep Test

Load are applied to the specimen through special end rotating grips. These grips are adopted to minimize the in-plane bending discussed by Pagano and Halpin (7). The hand-made creep testing machine is used as illustrated in Figure 3. Applying stress was determined in three levels under 40 % of a creep rupture stress (8) After the load applying, longitudinal and transverse directional strains are continuously recorded for twenty minutes .

VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF MATRIX AND REINFORCEMENT

The stiffness properties of a lamina can be characterized by specifying the value of E_{11} , E_{22} , , and G_{12} . Knowledge of these parameters specify both lamina and laminate properties. Accordingly it is these coefficients which we must predict from a knowledge of the reinforcement and matrix characteristics.

The first modulus to be determined is that of the lamina in the 1 direction in Figure 4. That is

$$E_{11} = E_f V_f + E_m' V_m \quad (9)$$

where $E_m' = E_m / (1 - 2\nu_m^2)$. Equation (9) is well known as the modified rule of mixtures expression (9) for the apparent Young's modulus in the fiber direction. In Equation (9), subscripts, f and m denote fibers and matrix, respectively. In the case that both matrix and fibers have a viscoelasticity, Equation (9) may be shown as the function of time as follows:

$$E_{11}(t) = E_f(t)V_f + E_m'(t)V_m \quad (10)$$

where $E_m'(t) = E_m(t) / (1-2\nu_m^2(t))$. The time dependent major Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{12}(t)$ can be given in the same manner. That is

$$\nu_{12}(t) = \nu_f(t)V_f + \nu_m(t)V_m \quad (11)$$

The apparent Young's modulus, E_{22} in the direction transverse to the fibers and in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} is well studied (10,11). Halpin and Tsai (12) who were able to show that Herman's solution (13) generalizing Hill's self approximate form. In this study, we incorporate time, t in their approximate form;

$$\frac{\bar{p}(t)}{p_m(t)} = \frac{1 + \xi \eta V_f}{1 - \eta V_f} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\eta = \left(\frac{p_f(t)}{p_m(t)} - 1 \right) / \left(\frac{p_f(t)}{p_m(t)} + \xi \right) \quad (13)$$

In Equations (12,13),

$\bar{p}(t)$; Time dependent lamina modulus, $E_{22}(t)$ or $G_{12}(t)$,
 $p_m(t)$; Time dependent matrix modulus, $E_m(t)$ or $G_m(t)$,
 $p_f(t)$; Time dependent fiber modulus, $E_f(t)$ or $G_f(t)$,

and

ξ denotes constant which shows the degree of reinforcement affected by the shape, arrangement and load condition of the fibers.

Our former investigation (14) indicates that $\xi=2$ is the best fitting for the same lamina or laminate of a construction. The short-term tensile creep test of FG284 polyester resin as used for a matrix of laminates shows $\eta = 0.26$ and $\log K = 2.667 + 0.022 \sigma$ in a longitudinal direction and $\log K = 2.279 + 0.025 \sigma$ in a transverse direction as shown in Figure 5. Also K value for the inplane shear creep stress are calculated by using the formula, $G = E / 2(1 - \nu)$. However the material property, K of glass fiber is approximately zero because that the fiber do not possess viscoelasticity in such a low level loading comparing to its rupture stress. Therefore the time dependent engineering constants of the lamina, $E_{11}(t)$, $E_{22}(t)$, $\nu_{12}(t)$ and $G_{12}(t)$ are calculated with Equations (10-13) and the above mentioned K values.

TIME DEPENDENT COMPLIANCES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL AND CROSS PLY LAMINATES ON FIBER DIRECTION

For a state of plane stress, only four principal creep compliances, $S_{11}(t)$, $S_{12}(t)$, $S_{22}(t)$, and $S_{66}(t)$ are needed to characterize the time dependent behavior of a unidirectional laminate or lamina. The stress-strain relation referred to the principal axes is expressed by the following formula:

$$\begin{vmatrix} e_1(t) \\ e_2(t) \\ e_3(t) \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} S_{11}(t) & S_{12}(t) & 0 \\ S_{12}(t) & S_{22}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66}(t) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{vmatrix} \quad (14)$$

and

$$S_{11}(t) = \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)}, \quad S_{22}(t) = \frac{1}{E_{22}(t)}, \quad S_{12}(t) = \frac{-\nu_{12}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} \quad (15)$$

$$S_{66}(t) = \frac{1}{G_{12}(t)}$$

In the case, that the fiber direction does not coincident to the load direction, time dependent strain, $e(t)$ in X-Y coordinate is:

$$|e(t)| = |\bar{S}_{ij}(t)| |\sigma| = |T|^T |S_{ij}(t)| |T| |\sigma| \quad (16)$$

where $|T|$ denotes the transformation matrix (5) and superscript T shows the transpose of the matrix. The time dependent strain, $e^o(t)$ for the cross ply laminate is given by

$$|e^o(t)| = |A_{ij}^1(t)| |N| \quad (17)$$

and

$$|A_{ij}^1(t)| = |A_{ij}(t)|^{-1} \quad (18)$$

where $|A_{ij}(t)|$ is the time dependent stiffness matrix for a laminate and $|N|$ shows stress resultant matrix.

Figure 6 shows the variation of the stiffness compliances at $t=0$ in various load direction and Figures 7-10 show the comparisons between experimental and calculated principal creep compliances of the unidirectional laminate. And also, Figures 11 and 12 show the time dependent compliances of the unidirectional laminate (U.D.L.) and cross ply laminate (C.P.L.) for various fiber angles and load levels, respectively. As the results, our calculated and analytical procedures have reasonable prediction of the time dependent viscoelasticity for the polyester/glass composites.

CONCLUSION

The results presented herein indicate that a polyester/glass composite has a large amount of anisotropic viscoelasticity even in a room temperature. It is likely that the results found are representative of other polymer based fiber reinforced composites. The two time dependent viscoelastic principal compliances of the unidirectional laminate, $S_{11}(t)$ and $S_{12}(t)$ are shown to be time independent. However other principal compliances, $S_{22}(t)$ and $S_{66}(t)$ indicate to be time dependent behavior. When the load direction does not coincident with a fiber direction, time dependent compliances for a unidirectional and cross ply laminates, $S_{11}(t)$ and $A_{11}(t)$ have a large amount of time dependent response.

The analytically predicted nonlinear viscoelastic equation based on thermodynamic theory shows the good agreement with experimental results. As the results, only two material information was needed to predict the nonlinear viscoelastic response of the composites, one is a viscoelastic response of the polyester resin. The other information is material constants of the polyester and glass fibers.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Fig. 1 Creep curve.

θ : Fiber Orientation

Fig. 2 Dimensions of the specimen.

Table 1 Materials of the specimen

Matrix Resin	Polyester Resin (Polilite FG-284, Dainippon Ink & Chemicals Inc.)
Reinforcement	E Glass Fiber (Micro Glass ERN, Nippon Glass Fiber Inc.)
Catalizer	Methyl Ethyl Keton per Oxide
Hardener	Cobalt Naphthenate 0.5% solution

Table 2 Stacking order of specimen

	Unidirectional laminate	Cross ply laminate
	U.D.L.	C.P.L. [+ θ , + θ -90°]
θ	0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 90°	10°, 20°, 45°
1st ply	+ θ	+ θ
2nd ply	+ θ	+ θ
3rd ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
4th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
5th ply	+ θ	+ θ
6th ply	+ θ	+ θ
7th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
8th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
9th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
10th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
11th ply	+ θ	+ θ
12th ply	+ θ	+ θ
13th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
14th ply	+ θ	+ θ -90°
15th ply	+ θ	+ θ
16th ply	+ θ	+ θ

Fig.3 Creep testing apparatus.

Fig.4 Lamina coordinate system

Fig.6 Variation of compliances at $t=0$ for various load direction.

Fig.5 Relation between viscoelastic factor, K and stress of FG-284 polyester resin.

Fig.7 Time dependent creep compliance, S_{11} of the unidirectional laminate.

Fig.8 Time dependent creep compliance, S_{12} of the unidirectional laminate.

Fig.9 Time dependent creep compliance, S_{22} of the unidirectional laminate.

Fig.10 Time dependent creep compliance, S_{66} of the unidirectional laminate.

Fig.12 Creep compliances of cross ply laminate (C.P.L.) for various stresses.

Fig.11 Creep compliance of unidirectional laminate (U.D.L.) for various stresses.